

THE CREATION OF ZAKHIRIDDIN BABUR’S CHARACTER IN THE NOVEL “RAIDERS FROM THE NORTH

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Abstract. *This article examines the first book of the epic novel “Empire of the Moghul” by the English writer Alex Rutherford, “Raiders from the North”, dedicated to the life of our great ancestor Zakhiriddin Babur. The issue of the creation of the personality of the great king and commander Babur as an image in the work is considered.*

Keywords: *Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, Amir Temur, Humayun Mirza, Shaybani Khan, Khanzodabegim, Samarkand, India, epic novel.*

Introduction. It is no secret to all of us that the history of our country Uzbekistan dates back thousands of years. Among the great figures who have made the Uzbek nation famous throughout the world, we can mention Al-Beruni, who achieved great heights in science, the unparalleled mathematician Al-Khwarizmi, and even Ibn Sina, who is recognized as the father of medicine today. But there is one person who not only contributed to the development of science, literature, and art, but also caused fundamental changes in world history with his unparalleled military skills. This person is our great ancestor Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur. His world fame is also evident in the interest shown in his life path by many European scientists and historians and the creation of countless scientific and artistic works. English writers such as Flora Annie Steel, Stephan Meredith Edwardes, Stephen Frederick Dale are among them. The topic of our doctoral thesis is devoted to studying the role of Babur Mirza and his later descendants, Humayun Mirza, Akbar, and Shahi Jahan Mirza, in historical processes.

Main part. Babur Mirza, who was just enjoying his childhood and having fun with his peers, was forced to take over the government of the country at the age of 12 due to the tragic death of his father, Umarshaikh Mirza, and give up his peace so that his people could live in peace, because this was his duty as the heir to the throne. Despite his young age, Babur captured the virgin city of Samarkand, the capital of the great commander Amir Temur. In such moments of joy, Babur’s speech to the people is very moving in the novel: *“He rose and turned slowly to face each side of the crowded square, allowing all to gaze up on their new king. Then he told the populace: “My rule will bring peace and prosperity to all the citizens of Samarkand. As a token of this, I will remit a month of the taxes levied on the city’s markets”. The crowd roared*

its approval. Though his own expression remained impassive, jubilation welled inside him again. Timur had been thirty-one, more than twice his age, when he had seized Samarkand. It had been his first great conquest, the springboard to a mighty empire. And so it would be for Babur”.¹ One can sense the high feelings of pride and arrogance in Babur's words. Here, the writer tries to compare Zahiriddin with his paternal ancestor, the commander Amir Temur, and in some sense tries to put him one step higher than Amir Temur, because the city that Babur captured at the age of only 13 was captured by his grandfather Temur at the age of 31.

As a result of Shaybani Khan's 100-day siege of Samarkand, not only ordinary people but also nobles suffered greatly. Seeing the citizens suffering from hunger, helplessness and disease, Babur finally decides to surrender. He escapes the enemy attack by transferring his sister Khanzada Begum to Shaybani Khan's harem: *“In the end he had had no real choice other than to agree to Shaibani Khan’s terms. It had clearly been the right thing to do for the sake of the citizens of Samarkand but the thought of retreat – of ceding the city to a hated foe – left a bitter taste in his mouth, like almonds left too long on the tree. Even so, this way he, too, would be free and have the opportunity to re-build his fortunes and those of his family, provided he retained his self-belief and determination which he knew he would. He was still a young man and had not been born or brought up to fail but to achieve great things. He would fulfil his destiny.*”² Tired of the blows of fate, suddenly losing both his homeland of Andijan and his lifelong dream of Samarkand, Zakhiriddin decides to redefine his life path and establish his own statehood in new lands.

Despite the fact that Babur founded a large state in the territory of present-day Afghanistan, why he suddenly wanted to conquer India is explained differently by different historians. Unfortunately, we cannot find an answer to this in the work “Baburnama”. Because the fragments of the unique work related to these years have been lost as a result of historical processes. The novel “Raiders from the North” contains the following ideas: *“Babur took another long drink and felt the wine flow through his body, freeing his tongue and his imagination. Suddenly an idea that had long been at the back of his mind crystallised: “Hindustan . . . that’s where I’d like to go. Do you remember Rehana’s story? If I captured treasure, as Timur did, no one, not Shaibani Khan or even the Shah of Persia, could stand in my way”.*³ The main reason for Babur's goal of conquering India is his desire to rule this country like his ancestor Amir Temur, and he also dreams of surpassing his main enemy at that time, Shaybani Khan, and the Iranian Shah Ismail. In this way, the author tries to instill in Babur's

¹ Alex Rutherford. Raiders from the North. – New York: St.Martin’s Press, 2010. – P. 96.

² Alex Rutherford. Raiders from the North. – New York: St.Martin’s Press, 2010. – P. 193.

³ Alex Rutherford. Raiders from the North. – New York: St.Martin’s Press, 2010. – P. 251.

character the qualities of a person who, along with bravery and taking a courageous step towards his goal, resorted to alcohol.

*“Having achieved so much, it was satisfying to reread some of the early passages of his diary, especially his despairing laments about his hopeless, throneless state and his yearnings for Samarkand. How ironic that he had not managed to hold Timur’s city long enough to create anything lasting whereas here, in Hindustan, he was building something permanent. When, eventually, he was called to Paradise, he would, God willing, leave his sons a rich and stable empire”.*⁴ From this excerpt from the work, we can understand that Babur Mirza was able to conquer a vast land like India and build a great empire, but even so, the pain and sorrow of leaving his homeland never left him. He always dreamed of “I wish I could establish a state like India in my own country.” It would have been like this if he had not surrendered Samarkand to his fierce enemy Shaybani Khan without a fight.

*“Humayun looked down at Timur’s heavy gold ring, an unaccustomed weight on his right hand, with the spitting, flat-eared tiger carved deep into the metal. It had seen so many conflicts, so many conquests . . . where would it travel with him? What glories, what disasters might it see while on his hand? That was not yet for him to know but, whatever happened, he would never bring dishonor on his dynasty or on his father’s memory. Raising the ring to his lips he kissed it and made a silent vow: “I will be a worthy successor to my father, and all the world will have cause to remember me”.*⁵ After the untimely death of Zahiriddin Babur Mirza at the age of 47, his son Humayun Mirza ascends the throne. He always tries to remember his father's teachings, be a just king for his people, and be a kind brother to his brothers and sisters. From the above passage, it can be understood that Humayun, like his father, sets himself the goal of becoming a worthy son for his ancestors. Taking the ring of Amir Temur, who has seen many battles over the centuries, Humayun Mirza swears not to do anything that will tarnish the name of his dynasty.

Conclusion. While reading the first book of the famous epic novel by Alex Rutherford, we witnessed how the English writer revealed the life path of Babur Mirza to the fullest. Just as there is no perfect person in this world, all the achievements and shortcomings of the king and the commander are fully shown to the readers.

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